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Critique about language, dialect and variation.

The relationship of language and society has evolved significantly affecting the way people behave and interact. It is said that when two or more people communicate in the same language or in the same speech that is called a system of communication, in which they basically are using signs, words, and gestures that create a combination which becomes into these codes in language that help speakers and listeners to understand messages . Messages are when; one receives the message, while the other is giving the message. In fact, when a person knows these to codes or dialects, the person is called bilingual. As matter of fact, bilinguals are able to communicate in their mother language and also in another language. Most of the time they have a mother language which is the one that they learned since they are born, speakers feel more comfortable speaking using their first language; for instance, it is better and easier to produce a smooth conversation in that language. Notwithstanding, the usage of their first language does not affect the interaction of their second language. The bilingual society are capable to communicate and share aspects properly of each language when expressing different ideas. Bilingual speakers´ competences are linked to their social aspects traits that they share in environment where they live.

The first aspect, it refers to language it is about how important speaking a language can be for humans. Is it necessarily an attribute that only humans may have? Explaining a language can be very challenging, humans have been trying to communicate themselves for years. The history shows that the beginning language or the dialects; let us say in this case, we were very confused. Ages ago, signs, drawings, and sounds could have meant a whole different system of dialogue. By that time there were no words, however these signs, drawings, and sounds are the oldest structure we knew, and it has been evolving through the years.

Consequently, there is no doubt that communication in a language is essential for human race; nevertheless, we cannot only attribute this language/communication to human beings exclusively; animals, plants, the whole world has its own way of communication. For sure, with a structure hard to interpret, to which obviously we have not developed yet. These dialects that we have are not a specific and unique attribute of us, the humans, what it is only ours, it is the possibility to motivate just by using our words, for instance, the impact on a person´s mind when a psychiatrist or a lawyer, even a teacher triggers only by using the right words in the right moment. It is totally different in each of them because they have a specific way to use the power of the language. The same case happens in communication for social relationships.

For instance, it is also very interesting to think that people get to spend the rest of their lives with a person who they do not have a background or a history with, anything at all, but the first engaging thing that people had was communication, the art of words many would agree. The technique or method that men use to talk to women, the way that men talk

to men, or women to women influence in a great way the opinion or the perception that person might have of them. The dialogue can build in people feelings such as love, hate, admiration or compassion, unbelievable, conversations create hope in people or an inexplicable pain with only words.

In general, we can say that people use the language or dialect that they speak for a variety of purposes; any person, any human being that is able to communicate, to express his or her hair ideas in a language, or into different system, he or she knows more mechanics of the language than any other book in the world. Until now and for many more years, any book can ever describe what a person possesses; the absolute knowledge the only person and its understanding which is their brain full of reasoning, that is the only person who can certainly speak the language. With all that being said, we understand the changes and concerns when it comes to talk about language in this current society, with all its dialects, and how it changes or variates through time.

References:

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